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32 (with doxyl-stearate spin labels) data revealed the existence of lamellar arrangements inside
33 the lipid nanoparticles, which was also confirmed also by SAXS experiments. Moreover
34 addition of dibucaine increased the molecular packing of both SLN and NLC lipids,
35 indicative of DBC insertion between the lipids, in the milieu assessed by the spin labels. Such
36 structural information brings insights into understanding the molecular organization of these
37 versatile drug-delivery systems, which have already demonstrated their potential for
38 therapeutic applications in pain control.

39 **Keywords:** solid lipid nanoparticles, nanostructured lipid carriers, local anesthetics,
40 electron paramagnetic resonance, small angle X-ray scattering, dibucaine.

41
42 **Abbreviations:** 5-doxyl-stearic acid (5-SASL); cetyl palmitate (CP); dibucaine (DBC);
43 electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR); Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR);
44 methyl-5-doxyl-stearic acid (5-MeSL); myristyl myristate (MM); nanostructured lipid
45 carriers (NLC); partition coefficient (P); small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS); solid lipid
46 nanoparticles (SLN); transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

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3 **51 Introduction**
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7 53 Nanostructured systems have been extensively investigated for anesthetic encapsulation
8 54 aiming both to increase bioavailability and to decrease local anesthetic toxicity. Solid lipid
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10 55 nanoparticles (SLN) and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC) offer an innovative alternative
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12 56 for the sustained release of local anesthetics (1-6). The development of these singular
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14 57 nanocarriers, however, demands careful structural characterization in order to identify the
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16 58 relevant architectural parameters, which could improve biological response. This
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18 59 understanding is fundamental in building a rationale towards more efficient drug
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20 60 formulations (7).

21 61 SLNs usually have poor drug loading efficiency, and drug expulsion is observed during
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23 62 storage. This drawback (drug leakage) is due to the rearrangement of the crystalline lipid
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25 63 core from a high-energy state to a more ordered (β) state on storage (8). Conversely, NLCs
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27 64 are less ordered structures, with higher drug loading and demonstrate good stability
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29 65 throughout their shelf life. NLCs differ from SLNs, in that a liquid lipid (at ambient
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31 66 temperature) is added to the solid lipid during preparation, favoring the formation of
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33 67 imperfections in the lipid matrix (9). This increases the intra-particle spaces available to the
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35 68 drug, resulting in greater encapsulation efficiency. It is the amorphous nature of NLCs that
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37 69 can reduce or avoid drug expulsion during storage (10-12). Recent works demonstrated that
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39 70 SLNs and/or NLCs are suitable nanocarriers for the incorporation of lipophilic drugs such
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41 71 as dibucaine, benzocaine, lidocaine, tetracaine, etomidate and prednisolone (1, 2, 13, 14).

42 72 Dibucaine (DBC) is an amine-amide type local anesthetic used for pain relief. It is one of
43
44 73 the most potent long-lasting local anesthetics, being fifteen times more potent than procaine
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46 74 (15-17). As other anesthetic agents, DBC reversibly blocks nervous transmission when
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48 75 applied to a specific region of the body, but it has limited water solubility – and this
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50 76 property restricts its use by the infiltrative route - and induces systemic toxicity (15).

51 77 The amine group of DBC has a pKa of 8.3 (18), which enables it to exist in both charged
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53 78 (protonated) and neutral (non-protonated) forms, at pH 7.4. Despite the voluminous
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55 79 isoquinoline ring of dibucaine, both ionization forms were found to interact with lipid
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57 80 bilayers, increasing the mobility of acyl chains and changing the polar heads of lipids (19)
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59 81 in liposomes.
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82 Other lipid-based nanocarriers are rather complex and understudied. So, developing further
83 knowledge about the soft core of SLN and NCL, and organization has important
84 implications in drug-delivery. Therefore, a detailed characterization of lipid nanocarriers
85 organization should be pursued. Structural insights should bring precious understanding to
86 these versatile systems, which have already demonstrated great potential for future
87 therapeutic applications in pain control.

88 89 **Experimental Section**

90 **Materials**

91 Dibucaine (DBC), poloxamer 188 (Pluronic F68), 5-doxyl-stearic acid and methyl-5-doxyl-
92 stearic acid spin labels (5-SASL and 5-MeSL, respectively) were obtained from Sigma-
93 Aldrich (St Louis, MO). Myristyl myristate (MM) and cetyl palmitate (CP) were from
94 Dhymers Fine Chemicals (Brazil) and Croda (Brazil), respectively. Liponate[®] GC (a
95 liquid lipid composed of a mixture of capric and caprylic acids) was supplied by Lipo do
96 Brazil (Brazil). Other reagents used were HPLC grade: acetonitrile (J.T. Baker, USA),
97 triethylamine (VETEC, Brazil), and orthophosphoric acid (Ecibra, Brazil). Deionized water
98 (18.2 MΩ cm) was obtained from a Waters ultrapure water system.

99 100 **Methods**

101 **Preparation of the lipid nanoparticles: solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured** 102 **lipid carriers**

103 Lipid nanoparticles (SLN and NLC) were produced by high pressure, hot homogenization
104 (*14*). Both SLN and NLC used in this study were prepared using either MM or CP at 2%,
105 w/v. In the case of NLC, Liponate[®] GC was used, at 0.5% w/w of the total lipid weight.
106 Briefly, lipids in the absence and presence of DBC (1 mg/mL) were heated to 49 or 64 °C,
107 i.e., 10 °C above the melting point of MM (39 °C) and CP (54 °C), respectively. In order to
108 form a microemulsion, the warmed lipid phase was added to a hot aqueous solution of
109 Poloxamer 188 (at 0.5 or 1.5% w/v for SLN and NLC, respectively), under high agitation
110 (10,000 rpm) in an Ultra-turrax T18 (IKA Werke Staufen, Germany) for 3 min. All samples
111 were further homogenized in a Panda 2k (Niro Soavi, Italy) equipment, with three 600 bar
112 cycles, and the formulations were cooled and stored at 4 °C (*20-23*).

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5 114 **Determination of size, polydispersity, and zeta potential**

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7 115 Particle size distribution and visual information of nanoparticles were obtained by
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9 116 nanoparticle tracking analysis, NTA (NanoSight LM20 and NTA 2.0 Analytical Software,
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11 117 NanoSight, Wiltshire, UK). 0.5 mL of diluted SLN or NLC samples (1:5,000 in milliQ water
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13 118 v/v) was injected into the chamber with a syringe, and samples were illuminated by a diode
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15 119 laser (635 nm wavelength). The Brownian motion of the individual particles was obtained in
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17 120 real time via a CCD camera, and analyzed using NTA 2.0 Analytical Software (NanoSight,
18
19 121 UK). Each video clip was captured for 10 s at 25 °C (24). Measures of the width of the
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21 122 distribution of particle size (SPAN) values were calculated by equation 1:
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23 124
$$Span = \frac{(D_{0.9} - D_{0.1})}{D_{0.5}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

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25 125 Where $d_{0.9}$, $d_{0.5}$, and $d_{0.1}$ are the particle diameters determined respectively at the 90th, 50th,
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27 126 and 10th percentile of undersized particles (25). The zeta potential was measured (at 25 °C)
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29 127 using capillary cells (10 mm with path lengths) in a Malvern Instruments Zetasizer Nano ZS
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31 128 (Worcestershire, UK). All samples were diluted in a solution of 0.1 mmol.L⁻¹ sodium
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33 129 chloride before analysis (sample/NaCl water ratio of 1:100, v/v). The number of
34
35 130 nanoparticles per mL of colloidal suspension analysis did not change when the samples were
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37 131 prepared with DBC. The results were expressed as the average ± standard deviation of three
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39 132 separate determinations, conducted one day after preparation.
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42 135 ***Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)***

43 136 The morphologies of the nanoparticles (SLN_{MM} and SLN_{CP} for solid lipid nanoparticles
44
45 137 composed of myristyl myristate and cetyl palmitate, respectively) and NLC_{MM}
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47 138 (nanostructured lipid carriers based on myristyl myristate), with and without DBC were
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49 139 examined using a transmission electron microscope (Zeiss LEO-906, 60 kV). 40 µL of each
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51 140 sample was added to a copper grid with 200 Mesh (Electron Microscopy Sciences) and left
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53 141 to rest for about 15 min. One drop of uranile solution (2%, m/m) was then added to improve
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55 142 the contrast of pictures obtained. Any excess of this solution was removed with filter paper
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57 143 (26).
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3 144 **Partition Coefficient determination**

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5 145 The partition coefficient (P) of DBC between nanoparticles and water was determined by
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7 146 phase separation (filtration-centrifugation): 0.3 ml of a SLN or NLC sample diluted in
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9 147 MilliQ water (2:100 v / v,) was transferred to a filtration unit with 10 kDa (Millex
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11 148 Millipore) and centrifuged for 20 minutes (4,100 x g, in a MC 12 V Sorval centrifuge). The
12
13 149 free DBC in the supernatant was quantified by HPLC, as described in (5).

14 150 The partition coefficient of DBC, i.e. the anesthetic ratio between two immiscible phases
15 151 (the lipid phase (l) and water phase (w)), was calculated using equation 2:

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$$P = \frac{\frac{n_l}{v_l}}{\frac{n_w}{v_w}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

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22 153 Where n= the number of moles of DBC and V is the volume of phases. The total number of
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24 154 moles of DBC in the sample was obtained from the sum of n_l and n_w . The lipid density was
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26 155 considered to equal 1 g.mL⁻¹ in order to estimate the volume of the lipid phase (16)
27 156 corresponding to 20 mg.mL⁻¹ of MM or CP (total the amount of solid lipid).

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31 158 **Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

32 159 SLN and NLC (with and without DBC) were frozen (*dry ice/ethanol* bath), and *lyophilized*
33 160 (Labconco, Freeze Dry System / FreeZone 4.5) over 24hrs. A Perkin Elmer 100 FTIR
34 161 spectrometer was used; the frequency range was 400-4000 cm⁻¹, with 32 scans per sample.
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36 162 1 mg of sample was mixed with solid potassium bromide and placed under pressed with a
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38 163 pressure of 10 tons using a hydraulic press to obtain transparent and thin pellets.

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43 165 **SAXS measurements**

44 166 SAXS experiments were performed at the National Laboratory of Synchrotron Light
45 167 (LNLS, Campinas, Brazil), with a radiation wavelength of 1,488 Å. The samples were
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47 168 studied using a detector distance of approximately ~1000 mm. The scattering curves were
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49 169 corrected (background subtracted). The scattering vector (q) was measured according to
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51 170 equation 3:

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53 171
$$q = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin\theta \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

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172 Where: 2θ is the scattering angle and λ the wavelength of X-rays.

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174 The sample exposure times varied from 2 to 5 minutes. The SLN_{CP} sample was subjected to
175 a heating process (30, 35, 40, 45 ° C), which was performed using a water bath under
176 thermostatic control. The remaining samples (SLN_{MM}, SLN_{MM}DBC and SLN_{CP}DBC) were
177 only run at room temperature. The dimensional information was aimed at the identification
178 of lamellar arrangement, as well as their periodicity (structural organization), and crystalline
179 or amorphous composition (27, 28).

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181 **Electron Paramagnetic Resonance experiments**

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The lipid milieu of SLN and NLC were analyzed from the spectra of two spin probes -5-SASL and 5-MeSL – of slightly different polarities, that were incorporated into the nanoparticles (SLN_{MM}, SLN_{CP} and NLC_{MM}) with and without DBC, up to 1 mole % (relative to total lipid concentration). Each spin label was incubated with the sample for approximately 30 mins, at 37 °C and the EPR spectra were recorded using a Bruker EMX spectrometer (Bruker BioSpin GmbH, Billerica) at 25 °C, and also from 5 - 55 °C. The order parameter (S), giving information on the orientation of the lipid core, considering lamellar structures, where the spin-label long molecular axis is roughly parallel to the normal bilayer, was calculated from the 5-SASL spectra, according to equation 4 (29):

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$$S = \frac{2A_{//} - 2A_{\perp}}{2[A_{zz} - (A_{xx} + A_{yy})/2]} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

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Where $A_{//}$ e A_{\perp} , measured directly from the EPR spectrum, are the hyperfine splitting for the spin label's long molecular axis oriented parallel and perpendicular, respectively to the external magnetic field. A_{zz} (32 Gauss), A_{xx} (6 Gauss) and A_{yy} (6 Gauss) were the principal components of the hyperfine tensor, measured in a single crystal (30). In lipid vesicles (liposomes), S describes the degree of organization in the bilayer, with values from 0 to 1, the unit revealing perfect anisotropy (long molecular axis parallel to the bilayer normal) (31). The spectra of 5-MeSL were analyzed in terms of an empirical parameter, ΔH_0 (width of the central line) (15). This parameter reports the contribution of both order and mobility in the spectra of spin label inserted into lipid phases. Lower ΔH_0 values correspond to lower order, higher mobility, or both. From hereon, the term organization will be employed to refer to the sum of both contributions (31, 32).

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3 204 **Statistical analysis**

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5 205 Statistical evaluation of size distribution used T (student) test, with a significance level of
6 206 5% ($p < 0.05$). The data was analyzed using Instat v.3 (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego,
7 207 CA, USA).
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12 209 **Results and Discussion**

13 210 Nanoparticle hydrodynamic diameters (in the absence and presence of DBC) were
14 211 evaluated by nanoparticle tracking analysis, NTA (Table 1). In this technique, all particles
15 212 were visualized by video recording (10 s) using a CCD camera. In the video frames the
16 213 largest particles are seen as defined bright dots and the smaller particles move more quickly
17 214 due to the Brownian motion of the particles (24, 33). Different light scattering intensities
18 215 were observed for each formulation, but the cumulative data in percentile of the particle
19 216 distribution indicated diameters of homogeneous size, *i.e.*, compatible with a single
20 217 population of particles.

21 218 The polydispersity of nanoparticles, measured from the Span index (equation 1, where the
22 219 lower the Span the narrower is the particle size distribution (34)) was ≤ 1 , confirming the
23 220 homogeneity of the system. The size and low polydispersity of the particles measured by
24 221 NTA are also in accordance with data obtained by dynamic light scattering (5).
25 222 Furthermore, there were no significant differences in particle size upon DBC addition
26 223 (Table 1). Total concentration of nanoparticles per mL laid between 2.46×10^8 to 7.7×10^8
27 224 in all formulations.
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41 226 Table 1. Average sizes (cumulative data of the diameter) of the lipid nanoparticles prepared
42 227 by high-pressure homogenization, as determined by NTA. D_{10} , D_{50} and D_{90} refer to the
43 228 diameters taken from the 10%, 50% and 90% of the cumulative distribution of particles.
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46 229 Statistic analysis: Student T test, $p < 0.05$, $n=3$.

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Samples	Cumulative distribution of diameters (D)			Average Diameter (nm)	Span
	D_{10} (nm)	D_{50} (nm)	D_{90} (nm)		
SLN_{MM}	118	178	248	172.00 ± 7.81	0.7
$SLN_{MM}DBC$	119	174	243	175.67 ± 10.69	0.7
SLN_{CP}	96	181	255	173.33 ± 5.13	0.9

<i>SLN_{CP}DBC</i>	80	148	234	178.00 ± 9.54	1.0
<i>NLC_{MM}</i>	134	178	242	178.67 ± 8.96	0.6
<i>NLC_{MM}DBC</i>	120	168	220	170.67 ± 3.79	0.6

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231 The steric stabilization provided by the non-ionic surfactant Pluronic F68 on the surface of
 232 the nanoparticles lead, in the absence of dibucaine, to zeta potentials in the range of -25 to -
 233 46 mV (Table 2). These values were enough to prevent nanoparticle aggregation and to
 234 ensure its stability (23). These results are consistent with those obtained by other research
 235 groups (23, 35), which produced SLN with a similar range of negative zeta values, that
 236 showed physical stability over two years of storage, justified by the addition of suitable
 237 steric stabilizers (36). The results presented in Table 2 also indicate that the surface of the
 238 nanoparticles become less negative when dibucaine is added to both SLN and NLC. Since
 239 the pKa of DBC is 8.3 (18), a significant amount of the positively charged anesthetic is
 240 present in the formulation (pH = 8.2), and it is reasonable to think that at least a fraction of
 241 DBC⁺ lies in the surface of the nanoparticles (18), turning the zeta potentials more positive.

242

243 Table 1. Zeta potential of the nanoparticles (SLN and NLC, with and without dibucaine,
 244 DBC), prepared with cetyl palmitate (CP) or myristil myristate (MM) by high-pressure
 245 homogenization; n=3.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Zeta potential (mV)</i>
SLN _{MM}	-26.91 ± 7.72
SLN _{MM} DBC	-18.47 ± 2.55
SLN _{CP}	-45.93 ± 4.64
SLN _{CP} DBC	-3.89 ± 0.96
NLC _{MM}	-28.83 ± 4.41
NLC _{MM} DBC	-14.89 ± 2.78

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247 The morphology of SLN_{MM}, SLN_{CP} and NLC_{MM}, particles were found to be very similar:
 248 approximately spherical, with well-delineated contours, and homogeneous size distribution
 249 in the range of 200-250 nm (Figure 1). Incorporation of DBC did not affect the
 250 morphology or size of the nanoparticles, as exemplified for NLC_{MM} (Figure 1). Moreover,

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3 251 the micrographs also confirmed the results obtained by NTA, regarding the size of the
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5 252 nanoparticles.

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18 253 Figure 1. TEM micrographs of the solid lipid nanoparticles prepared by high-pressure
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20 254 homogenization: (A). NLC_{MM}, (B). NLC_{MMDBC}. Magnification of 100,000x (left) and
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22 255 60,000x (right).
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26 257 It is known that the higher the aqueous solubility, the faster the anesthetic distributes and
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28 258 reaches the biological membrane, being more rapidly removed from the site of action,
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30 259 favoring the cessation of the pharmacological effect. On the other hand, the higher the lipid
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32 260 solubility of the anesthetic agent, the greater is its penetration in the nerve membrane
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34 261 where they concentrate and exert their biological effect.

35 262 In that sense, the partition coefficients (P) of DBC between the oily (SLN or NLC) and
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37 263 aqueous phases were determined, according to equation 2. The obtained P values were
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39 264 high, and statistically different between SLN and NLC nanoparticles (ANOVA, Tukey-
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41 265 Kramer test, $p < 0.05$): 11510 ± 3949 for SLN_{MMDBC}, 13225 ± 4954 for SLN_{CPDBC} and
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43 266 31527 ± 3487 for NLC_{MMDBC}.

44 267 High P values are desirable, as they are directly correlated with the anesthetic potency of
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46 268 the formulation (37, 38). Moreover, the P values determined here are one order of
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48 269 magnitude higher than those reported for other lipid-based drug delivery systems (egg
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50 270 phosphatidylcholine liposomes: 1920 at pH 7.4, (19)), attesting the extraordinary loading
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52 271 efficiency of SLN and NLC over liposomes. Additionally, nanostructured lipid carriers
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54 272 (containing a blend of lipids in their core) produce less crystalline structures than solid
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56 273 lipid nanoparticles, being more stable over the time (9, 39). As expected, the partition of

274 DBC between NLC_{MM}DBC/water is 2-3 times higher than that between
275 SLN_{MM}DBC/water, confirming the high drug loading (40) of the first.

276
277 As a first approach to gain an insights into the interaction of DBC with the nanoparticles,
278 Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy was used. The FTIR spectra of free DBC, the
279 physical mixture of the SLN components plus DBC (Fig. 2 B, C), SLN_{MM}DBC (Fig. 2D)
280 and SLN_{CP}DBC (Fig. 2 E) revealed that the main absorption bands of DBC were observed
281 in all of the samples.

282
283 Figure 2. FTIR spectra (in KBr pellets) of: DBC (A); its physical mixture with the SLN
284 components: myristil mirystate (B) or cetyl palmitate (C) plus Pluronic F68 and DBC,
285 SLN_{MM}DBC (D) and SLN_{CP}DBC (E).

286
287 However, comparing the spectra of DBC in the physical mixture and SLN formulations,
288 there were no significant displacements of the main DBC bands (stretching bands: O-H at
289 3412 cm⁻¹; N-H at 3286 cm⁻¹, C=O at 1642-1574 cm⁻¹ and quinoline ring C=C at 1547 cm⁻¹),
290 suggesting a weak interaction between the drug and the SLN, probably because DBC
291 was only dissolved in the lipid matrix. Similar observations were reported by Araújo and
292 coworkers (41) for NLC associated with triamcinolone, suggesting that no chemical

293 interaction took place between the corticosteroid and the lipid matrix, and that triamcinolone
 294 was just dissolved in the lipid matrix of the particle.
 295 A multiple-phase system such as SLN and NLC, with different densities of electrons and
 296 nanometric dimensions, can be dissected by *X-ray scattering* techniques, which provides
 297 important information as to their molecular organization. The peaks observed in SAXS
 298 diffractograms are associated with the presence of ordered phases, such as liquid crystals, for
 299 example. From the peak position, one can calculate the *repeat* distances and finally obtain
 300 the frame type of the system (27). Consequently, the use of the SAXS aimed at a better
 301 understanding of the structural organization of the lipids that form the core of SLN and NLC.
 302 Figure 3A shows the scattering intensity curve, as a function of the scattering q vector, for
 303 the SLN_{CP}DBC sample. Two peaks could be observed at 1.61 and 1.44 nm⁻¹, with repeating
 304 intervals. These peaks are characteristic of CP nanoparticles and therefore represent the
 305 specific arrangements of the cetyl palmitate lipids within the nanoparticles. The peaks are
 306 located at periodic distances, with the same repeat interval, being compatible with the
 307 arrangement of a multi-lamellar lipid structure (28). Moreover, they have the bilayer core-to-
 308 bilayer core distances of 38.9 angstroms (lamellar phase I) and 43.5 angstroms (lamellar phase
 309 II) (Figure 3 A).

310

(A)

(B)

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312 Figure 3. SAXS: Scattering intensity vs. q vector in: A) $SLN_{CP}DBC$, measured at increasing
 313 (20, 30 and 40 °C) temperatures, and B) in a SLN_{CP} sample, with and without DBC,
 314 at 20 °C.

315

316 The existence of lamellar arrangements inside SLN/NLC may sound strange since this
 317 requires the presence of water molecules inside the nanoparticle. For example, if we take
 318 serum lipoproteins as a model, whose lipid core is formed by triglycerides and cholesterol-
 319 esters (42), these nonpolar molecules form lipid droplets inside the particles. But that is not
 320 the case with SLN and NLC . The hydrophilic-lipophilic balance of MM and CP (the major
 321 components of the lipid core) is significant, explaining why these lipids would not be
 322 comfortable in the absence of water. Despite the crystalline organization of solid lipids inside
 323 SLN described by calorimetric measurements, evidence pertaining to on the existence of
 324 lamellar lipid phases inside SLN was also available in the literature (27, 28, 43-45). For
 325 instance Lukowski and coworkers (27), and de Souza et al. (28) demonstrated by SAXS that
 326 cetyl palmitate, as well as stearic acid lipids are organized in lamellae inside SLN . These
 327 authors also suggested that compounds incorporated into SLN could be stored between these
 328 bilayers. Fig. 3A shows that at fixed temperatures, below 30 °C, structural changes were
 329 observed. However, above this temperature just small changes were visualized (e.g. the
 330 disappearance of a peak at $q_3 = 2.9$ observed in curves performed at 30
 331 °C and a reduction in the intensity of formed peaks), but without compromising the internal

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3 332 structure of the particle (Fig. 3 A). There were no changes in the SAXS diffractograms of
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5 333 SLN measured in the absence, or in the presence of dibucaine (Fig. 3 B).
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8 335 Electron Paramagnetic Resonance was another spectroscopic technique employed to
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10 336 identify the effect of DBC on the mobility and organization of the lipid core of the
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12 337 nanoparticles. For that purpose, stearic acid-derivatives spin labels (5-SASL and 5-MeSL)
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14 338 were inserted in the lipid milieu of SLN and NLC, to monitor the molecular arrangements
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16 339 of MM and CP.

17 340 Since SAXS results gave indications as to the existence of bilayers inside the nanoparticles,
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19 341 we have applied EPR concepts on the membrane (bilayers) structure to obtain information
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21 342 about DBC effect inside the lipid core of SLN and NLC. In membranes at high
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23 343 temperatures, if the degree of order of the bilayer is small, the external extremes in the
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25 344 spectrum are not resolved and the order parameter cannot be directly measured. In this case,
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27 345 one can monitor the width of the central line (ΔH_0), a measure indirectly related to the
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29 346 bilayer fluidity. So ΔH_0 is a parameter resulting from the orientation and rotational mobility
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31 347 contribution of the spin label inserted into a bilayer (30).

32 348 As for the 5-doxyyl stearate spin label (5-SASL), when inserted in bilayers, it monitors
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34 349 regions closer to the polar head group, due to the high polarity of the stearic acid (46). The
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36 350 spectra of 5-SASL in SLN_{MM} and SLN_{CP} are given in Figure 4, while Figure 5 depicts the
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38 351 changes in H_0 as a function of temperature.

39 352 The spectra on Fig. 4 reveal a high degree of anisotropy below 30 °C, and is compatible
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41 353 with the bilayer arrangement (47), confirming the SAXS data. The second lane of Figure 4
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43 354 shows that the presence of DBC broadens the SASL signal in SLN_{MM} , increasing ΔH_0 at
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45 355 temperatures below 30 °C (first lane, left spectrum), which indicates a higher degree of
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47 356 anisotropy in the chemical ambience monitored by the spin label. The effect of DBC in the
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49 357 spectrum of 5-SASL is even more evident at lower temperatures (5, 10 °C), where there is a
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51 358 separation in the low field peak components, as indicated by the arrows over the spectrum.

52 359 The opposite is seen at temperatures above the melting temperature of MM (39 °C): from
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54 360 40 to 55 °C, the presence of DBC favors the isotropy of lipids in the region monitored by 5-
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56 361 SASL, leading to minor values of ΔH_0 (Figure 5). Such results reveal a biphasic effect for
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3 362 DBC over SLN_{MM} particles: increasing the lipid milieu order below the melting point of the
4 lipid that forms the SLN core, and fluidizing the bilayer arrangement, above it.

5 363
6 364 This effect was confirmed when 5-SASL was incorporated into SLN_{CP}, with and without
7 DBC (Figure 4, third and fourth lanes, and Figure 5) (31). Since the melting point of CP is
8 365 higher (54 °C) than that of MM (25, 28, 48), DBC only induced the widening of the
9 366 spectra, because the measurements were carried out below the melting point of cetyl
10 367 palmitate.
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12 368 palmitate.

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40 371 Figure 4: EPR spectra of 5-SASL incorporated in SLN_{MM} and SLN_{CP} in the absence and
41 presence of DBC (molar ratio of 16:1 for MM:DBC and 13:1 for CP:DBC), measured at
42 372 different temperatures. Total spectra width 100G. The central field line width, ΔH_0 , is
43 373 indicated.
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376 Figure 5: Center field line width, ΔH_0 , from EPR spectra of 5-SASL incorporated in: (A)
 377 SLN_{MM} and (B) SLN_{CP}, in the absence and presence of DBC (molar ratio of 16:1 for
 378 MM:DBC and 13:1 for CP:DBC) at all studied temperatures (from 5 to 55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

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380 We have also measured the segmental order parameter (S) in the 5-SASL spectra inserted
 381 in SLN and NLC. The order parameter of SLN_{CP} at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($S = 0.62$) was greater than that
 382 of SLN_{MM} ($S = 0.47$), indicating higher lipid packing in the nanoparticles composed of
 383 cetyl palmitate, as expected due to its longer acyl chain length (regarding MM). As
 384 evidenced by the increased ΔH_0 observed below 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 5), the S values measured at
 385 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the presence of DBC increased to 0.66 for SLN_{MM} DBC and 0.68 for SLN_{CP} DBC,
 386 confirming the higher degree of anisotropy in the chemical ambience monitored by the spin
 387 label. So, the presence of DBC determines a rearrangement of the lipids in the SLN core,
 388 increasing the molecular orientation of both MM and CP bilayers. These EPR results

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389 provided unequivocal evidences of the insertion of DBC into the core region of both MM
 390 and CP solid lipid nanoparticles, as monitored by the 5-SASL paramagnetic probe (31).
 391 EPR spectra were also run for NLC samples. As expected, the mix of liquid lipids with
 392 MM and CP determined a less organized arrangement in the NLC lipid core, curbing the
 393 measure of S values in those nanoparticles. Figure 6 put together the EPR results (ΔH_0
 394 values) measured in the spectra of the spin labels 5-SASL and 5-MeSL incorporated in the
 395 different nanoparticles (SLN_{MM} , $SLN_{MM}DBC$, SLN_{CP} , $SLN_{CP}DBC$, NLC_{MM} and
 396 $NLC_{MM}DBC$) at 25 °C. 5-MeSL is the methyl ester of 5-SASL, and in liposomes it
 397 monitors deeper regions of the bilayer (47). As expected, 5-MeSL (Figure 6, left), being
 398 less polar than 5-SASL (Figure 6, right), is inserted deeper into the nanoparticles' bilayers,
 399 resulting in more isotropic spectra (narrower and less separated spectral lines) than those of
 400 5-SASL. Both labels detected the partition DBC into SLN and NLC bilayers, increasing the
 401 molecular packing at lower temperatures. But 5-SASL was more sensitive to the effect of
 402 DBC than 5-MeSL, indicating that DBC preferentially inserts in the vicinity of the polar
 403 head group region of the bilayers.

404 Figure 6. (A) EPR spectra and (B) ΔH_0 values in the spectra of 5-SASL and 5-MeSL
 405 inserted into SLN_{MM} , $SLN_{MM}DBC$, SLN_{CP} , $SLN_{CP}DBC$, NLC_{MM} and $NLC_{MM}DBC$, at 25
 406 °C.
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3 409 In lamellar systems such as liposomes, the spectra of 5-MeSL monitor a less structured
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5 410 region than 5-SASL, which is assigned to its deepest insertion into the bilayer, to a less
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7 411 organized region (15, 49). Also in bilayers, a 5-MeSL spin label was used to monitor the
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9 412 effect caused by the partition of the neutral form of different local anesthetics in egg
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11 413 phosphatidylcholine liposomes (15). All the nine ester and amino-amide anesthetics,
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13 414 including dibucaine, caused a decrease in ΔH_0 values when inserted to the same molar ratio
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15 415 (1:3 anesthetic:lipid) in the bilayer. But only when the membrane was treated with high
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17 416 amounts of the amino-ester type (chlorprocaine, procaine and tetracaine) anesthetics, the
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19 417 appearance of an additional spectral component was detected, accompanied by a lower
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21 418 anisotropy. This additional spectral component, more immobilized and observed here in the
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23 419 SLN_{MM}DBC sample below 35 °C (Fig. 4 and 6), was assigned to the spin label partitioning
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25 420 into a lipid-phase enriched of anesthetic, responsible for the largest local lipid packaging. It
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27 421 is worthwhile noting that the protonated form of DBC has aggregative properties (19) and
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29 422 that AFM data evidenced the formation of mixed (bilayer-micelle) structures when DBC
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31 423 was added to planar membranes of dimyristoyl phosphatidylcholine (18).
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33 424 Therefore, EPR data revealed that dibucaine partitions in all formulations studied, caused
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35 425 an increase in the molecular organization of lipids at the inner lipid core of the particles, in
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37 426 the regions monitored by the spin labels (5-SASL and 5-MeSL). Considering that the lipid
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39 427 arrangement within SLN and NLC core is lamellar (as suggested by SAXS and EPR
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41 428 results), the greatest packaging occurs by DBC insertion between the lipids that comprise
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43 429 the bilayer, within a depth compatible with the position of the labels (that contain a
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45 430 nitroxide radical attached to the fifth carbon of stearic acid or its methyl derivative).
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47 431 EPR spectra were also used to monitor the stability of the lipid arrangement of SLN and
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49 432 NLC upon addition of the anesthetic, following heating and cooling of nanoparticles. The
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51 433 hysteresis of the formulations (SLN_{MM}, SLN_{MM}DBC, SLN_{CP} and SLN_{CP}DBC) was
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53 434 assessed by evaluating ΔH_0 values of 5-SASL spectra after heating / cooling / reheating
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55 435 cycles. The results showed that in SLN_{MM}, with and without dibucaine, the chemical
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57 436 environment monitored by the 5-SASL probe is the same and there is no measurable lipid
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59 437 reorganization (no spectral change) as a function of temperature, but for the transition
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438 temperature of the lipid, at ca. 40 °C (data not shown). In SLN_{CP}, a small difference was
439 observed in the measured ΔH_0 after cooling the sample containing DBC, indicating a

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3 440 change in the likely partition of DBC molecules according to the thermal modification of
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5 441 the system. In any case, the change was not significant, such that SLN_{CP} can be considered
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7 442 as a stable formulation in relation to DBC partition.
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10 444 **Conclusion**

11 445 In this work, solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured lipid carriers containing dibucaine
12 446 were successfully prepared. The lipid nanoparticles were composed of cetyl palmitate or
13 447 myristil myristate as the solid lipid matrices, Pluronic F68 as the steric stabilizer and
14 448 contained (NLC) or not (SLN) a small proportion of liquid lipid (a triglyceride of capric
15 449 and caprylic acids). DBC effect on the structural organization of the nanoparticles was also
16 450 evaluated. Using a high-pressure homogenization method particles with ca. 200 nm and
17 451 high drug loading were obtained. DBC partition into SLN (SLN_{MMDBC} and SLN_{CPDBC})
18 452 and NLC_{MM} was very high ($> 10^4$), in accordance with the lipophilicity of the anesthetic.
19 453 SAXS results indicated the existence of lamellar lipid arrangements inside both SLN and
20 454 NLC. FTIR spectra did not provide any evidence of the interaction between DBC and the
21 455 lipids, but EPR measurements confirmed the lamellar lipid organization of both SLN and
22 456 NLC. It also revealed that dibucaine partitions into the lipid core of the nanoparticles,
23 457 promoting greater molecular organization of the lipids, in the moiety monitored by the spin
24 458 labels (5-SASL and 5-MeSL), at temperatures below the melting point of the solid lipid.
25 459 The results show the complementation of biophysical and pharmaceutical approaches in the
26 460 characterization of a potential innovative formulation for the treatment of pain.
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3 612 **Table of Contents**

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